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A Case Study for Unveiling Flexibility Options in Achieving Swiss National Energy Goals

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Abstract

This paper examines the possibilities and crucial importance of leveraging flexibility within the Swiss electricity grid against the backdrop of the national energy targets for 2050. This case study focusses on an in-depth analysis around three low voltage transformers and corresponding 15min load/consumption measurements. The potential of flexibility as an imperative for ensuring a resilient and adaptive energy infrastructure is analysed.

The study focusses on opportunities for applying flexibility within the grid, emphasizing its pivotal role in mitigating challenges associated with the integration of renewable energy sources and the growing demand for electricity. The investigation delves into future energy flows based on Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) scenarios.

A detailed exploration of the historic 2023 metering data at the transformer level in the pilot area provides a foundation for the subsequent analysis, where multiple scenarios for the low voltage grid and the corresponding three transformers are outlined. The literature indicates that flexibility can be instrumental in addressing overloading risks and potential disruptions, especially during critical periods such as cold winter periods or sunny spring days. Our results reveal a concerning trajectory post-2030, indicating that without proactive measures, the transformers are susceptible to overloading – Although only for a few hours each year. This poses the question on whether a smart approach using demand side flexibility could avoid or delay costly grid extension measures.

This study seeks to not only contribute to the academic discourse on the topic but also serve as a practical guide for policymakers, grid operators, and energy providers. By illuminating the possibilities and opportunities for using flexibility, this contribution aims to inspire informed decisions in the pursuit of a secure, sustainable, and flexible energy supply for Switzerland's future.

Introduction

As the world transitions towards a low-carbon energy future and we stand at the crossroads of an energy evolution, characterised by a surging demand for electricity and an unprecedented transition towards sustainability, flexibility emerges as a pivotal factor in the resilience and adaptability of our power systems.

This paper explores the multifaceted importance of flexibility in addressing the challenges posed by the growing demand for electricity and the integration of intermittent renewable energy sources. Further, the feasibility of utilising flexibility in the ENFLATE project's pilot area will be analysed.

The Swiss national energy targets for 2050 aim to achieve a 90% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and a shift to almost 100% renewable energy. A pivotal element of this strategy involves transitioning the electricity supply from large, centralised power plants to smaller, decentralised assets. Simultaneously, the heating and mobility sector is decarbonised by electrification. The growing integration of photovoltaics (PV), heat pumps, and electric vehicles (EVs) in Switzerland imposes various challenges on the country's electricity grid. The Swiss energy transformation assigns an entirely novel role to the electricity grids. Especially the low voltage levels are affected. Fortunately, at least some of these challenges posed to the existing grid infrastructure can be mitigated by deploying load-side flexibility in a smart way [1].

Flexibility in energy systems involves adjusting electricity supply or demand to match varying levels of renewable energy generation. This adjustment may be achieved through measures such as interconnection, demand response, storage, and flexible generation in power plants.

In 2022, the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) developed the scenario framework 2030/2040 [2]. It is based on the Swiss national "Energy Perspectives 2050+". Currently, three scenarios are being considered, differing in the combination of technologies and the pace of transition to renewable energy sources in the electricity sector. These scenarios are:

- **"Reference" scenario 1:** This scenario prioritises a substantial electrification of the energy system and a rapid expansion of domestic renewable electricity production. Electric demand is expected to significantly increase as EVs and heat pumps become more common.
- **"Divergence" scenario 2:** This scenario foresees an even more substantial increase in electricity consumption combined with a delayed expansion of domestic production. This increase could lead to increased reliance on imported electricity and potentially higher electricity prices.
- **"Sector coupling" scenario 3:** This scenario assumes a more critical role for biogas and synthetic gases and a more rapid expansion of PV. These assumptions lead to a more decentralised energy system.

Table 1 below provides an overview of the most important indicators for the target years 2030 and 2040 at the national level. Substantial differences in electricity production and consumption will become genuinely apparent in 2040. Conventional electricity consumption will be reduced by around 15-18% in scenarios 1 and 3 and by around 8% in scenario 2 by 2040. This is attributed to efficiency measures in lighting, electrical appliances and building technology and by replacing direct electricity heating and electric boilers.

Table 1 - Overview of key indicators 2030/2040 for scenarios 1–3.
Source: SFOE Scenario framework for electricity network planning [2]

Year	2019	2030			2040		
		Sc. 1	Sc. 2	Sc. 3	Sc. 1	Sc. 2	Sc. 3
Electricity production							
PV installed capacity [MW]	2 520	9 770	7 650	12 210	24 070	10 100	30 090
Electrification							
EVs incl. plug-in hybrids*, number [thousand]	40	930	980	870	2 940	3 230	2 520
Heat pumps incl. large heat pumps*, [TWh]	2,44	6,81	7,15	5,53	9,79	10,77	6,96
Electricity consumption							
Household sector without heat pumps, energy volume [TWh]	17,25	14,60	15,33	14,66	12,99	14,28	13,08

The following sections aim to provide a visual understanding of the transformer loading in different scenarios, offering insights into the potential challenges and opportunities.

1. Characterisation of 2023 transformer loading based on historic smart meter data

This section investigates the implications of these scenarios for the Swiss electricity grid, focusing on the two neighbouring villages, "Henau" and "Jonschwil" in eastern Switzerland, which were chosen as pilot areas within the ENFLATE project [3].

There are three low-voltage transformers located within the pilot areas:

- One transformer in Henau with 400 kVA (which could potentially be upgraded to 630 kVA in the coming years)
- Two transformers are located in Jonschwil, each with 630 kVA nominal capacity.

The remainder of this section aims to analyse repercussions related to the growing integration of PV, heat pumps, and EVs in both pilot areas on the distribution grid throughout the period spanning the next two decades according to the SFOE Scenario framework. First, historic smart meter data is compiled as baseline. Second, the historic load is split into its individual components (PV, EVs, heat pumps, residual load). Third, these individual components are scaled to 2030 and 2040 according to the Swiss national energy transition goals.

The historic 2023 metering data is collected and aggregated at the transformer level. The PV generation data and the total load are directly measured by all 419 smart meters in the pilot areas. Availability of Heat pumps and EVs data until July 2023 allows to split the total demand side into components: (1.) Heat pumps, (2.) EVs, and (3.) the residual load as it can be seen at Figure 1.

Figure 1 – 2023 smart meter data aggregated at the transformer in Henau

Figure 2 depicts the loading over a few critical days specific to the transformer in Henau that were indicated with red rectangles on Figure 1. The left-hand side of Figure 2 depicts cold winter days characterised by elevated energy consumption from EVs and heat pumps. The date range on the horizontal axis is chosen as the coldest three days in 2023, with the highest daily consumption measured. The right-hand side showcases three sunny spring days with increased PV production. The dates on the horizontal axis are chosen as the days with the highest irradiation values recorded in 2023.

Figure 2 - 2023 smart meter data aggregated at the transformer in Henau for the two extreme periods: Cold winter days with high consumption (left), and sunny spring days with high PV infeed (right)

The data-extracting process for disaggregating the total demand side into components is shown in Figure 3. The heat pump component is estimated using non-intrusive load monitoring (NILM). A NILM algorithm from the DOMOs project [4] is deployed to extract the heat pump time-series load profiles from the total load.

Since the EV penetration today remains very close to zero, the time-series data for EVs is based on a dataset of 300+ cars from another measurement campaign outside the pilot area [5] and scaled to fit the pilot perimeters. The residual load is defined as the remaining load not assigned to heat pumps or EVs. Therefore, the residual load mainly consists of electric boilers, heating, kitchen equipment, lighting, etc.

Figure 3 – Sketch of data extraction process from 15min smart meter data to its NILM components. Since PV is measured separately in the smart meter, only the consumption curve has to be split into three subcomponents using NILM

Figure 4 illustrates the status of the Henau transformer as of the year 2023, encompassing analysis of PV data, heat pumps, EVs, and residual load data, with the total summed at the transformer in kilowatts (kW). This transformer is operating well within its nominal operational limits as of 2023.

Figure 4 - Overview of 2023 situation at the transformer Henau based on historic metering value. Non-intrusive load monitoring algorithms are used to split the overall load into three components: heat pumps, electric vehicle charging, and the residual load.

2. Simulation of uptake scenarios

This section extrapolates the historic energy flows to 2030 and 2040 by scaling the historic metering data according to the SFOE scenarios. The purpose of the simulation is to examine how many years into the future grid reinforcement measures, or the use of flexibility will become critically important. It is assumed that the uptake of PV, EV, heat pumps, and residual load in the pilot area is directly proportional to the national uptake levels. The scenario interpolation process is shown in Figure by the example of heat pump uptake. The SFOE scenarios contain data points for 2019, 2030 and 2040. Therefore, coefficients for linear interpolation to 2019 are derived from data starting in 2023 (step 1). Steps 2 and 3 relate to the extrapolation towards the target years 2030 and 2040.

Figure 5 – Linear interpolation of heat pump uptake from 2023 to 2030 and 2040

In Figure 6, the results of all three SFOE scenarios for the transformer in Henau are presented for 2030. The linear scaling coefficient from Figure 5 is applied to all 2023 load curves. For each SFOE scenario [2], different coefficients apply, indicating the uncertainty interval. The lefthand column displays cold winter days with high energy consumption. The righthand column shows sunny spring days with lots of PV infeed and almost no load.

Figure 6 - Loading of the transformer Henau extrapolated to 2030. Gray lines correspond to historic 2023 measurement as baseline, while red lines indicate the transformer's current operational limits. The shaded blue area represents the range of SFOE scenarios 1 to 3.

Figure 7 shows the results for Henau extrapolated to 2040. Please note that the 400 kVA transformer has been upgraded to a 630 kVA unit.

Figure 7 - Loading of the transformer Henau extrapolated to 2040

Figure 8 illustrates the 2040 scenario results for one transformer in Jonschwil. The data includes information on PV generation, heat pumps, EVs, and residual load, aggregated at transformer level.

Figure 8: Loading of one transformer in Jonschwil extrapolated to 2040.

3. Flexibility in action

To investigate the potential of flexibility to postpone or avoid costly grid reinforcements, this chapter investigates a highly simplistic strategy for activating flexibility. Aim is to get a feeling for the effects on the grid loading by shifting the consumption of heat pumps and EV and curtailing PV infeed. The strategy is applied to the two critical time periods identified in Figure 1.

For heat pumps and EV, a maximum allowable power consumption limit is established. When this limit is reached, the excess energy consumption is shifted to later time periods. Specifically, when the consumption limit is reached during winter evening hours, EV charging is rescheduled to later hours. This redistribution considers the necessary time by which all EVs must be fully charged, ensuring that charging is completed within the required timeframe without exceeding transformer limits. For the solar energy generated by PV systems, production caps are implemented when generation levels exceed transformer limits. It is assumed that a centralised control entity at the transformer level dispatches each asset per asset group such that the maximum power limit is perfectly respected and perfectly tracked.

Figure 9: Resulting 2040 transformer loading for Henau when a combination of load shifting and PV curtailment is used to manage the transformer load during critical hours on critical days. Gray lines represent the SFOE scenario 1 for 2040 without flexibility measures. Blue lines show the load with curtailment implemented for heat pumps and EVs, and PV.

4. Analysis and interpretation of results

In the context of the scenario results for the year 2030 presented in Figure 6, the results indicate that without counteraction the transformer Henau will exceed its nominal operational limits around 2030. This underscores the critical importance of proactive measures and strategic planning to address potential challenges in ensuring the longevity and reliability of the grid infrastructure.

In Figure 7, the visual representation of the year 2040 scenario unveils a concerning situation at the transformer Henau. Particularly during cold winter days, overloading surpasses the transformer limits. Obviously, curtailing PV infeed alone will not help on critically cold winter days.

In the Jonschwil area, a situation like Henau is observed. An example of this is illustrated in Figure 8, focusing on one of the transformers in Jonschwil and depicting the predicted working conditions of the transformer in the year 2040. The findings indicate that by 2030, the transformer will be operating close to its normal limits. However, it is noteworthy that a few years after 2030, the transformer will undoubtedly exceed its operational limits.

An upgrade of the existing 400 kVA transformer in Henau with a 630 kVA unit is only a temporary solution, as this measure alone will not resolve all issues until 2040. This emphasises the need to unlock demand response to ensure the resilience of the electrical infrastructure.

Figure 9 shows that, without flexibility measures, the transformer experiences up to four hours of minor overload during a cold winter day. During a sunny spring day, six hours of considerable overload is displayed. Results provide a preliminary assessment of the flexibility effect on the transformer loading.

Despite the high simplistic nature of the deployed load shifting and curtailment strategy, the number of hours with overloading is reduced to zero. Certainly, more advanced load shifting strategies could reduce the transformer loading further. It is worth noting that the PV curtailment yielded more substantial results than the load shifting.

Considering above findings, it becomes evident that the utilisation of flexibility is an appealing option to avoid renewable curtailment and delay costly grid reinforcement measures.

As we look ahead, the significance of flexibility becomes increasingly apparent, urging a comprehensive and forward-thinking approach to grid management. Solutions may involve harnessing flexibility, especially shifting energy consumption of EVs, heat pumps, and other loads.

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